

have been reported by us earlier (this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 543). These were prepared by condensing quaternary salts containing reactive methyl groups (4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide) with diphenylformamidine in acetic anhydride. In the present investigation, by replacing diphenylformamidine in the latter reaction by β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride, acetanilido compounds such as (I : $n = 2$), and by glutaric aldehyde dianilide hydrochloride, compounds such as (I : $n = 3$), have been successfully synthesised.

These acetanilido compounds have been subsequently condensed with reactive ketomethylene compounds (3-ethylrhodanine) in presence of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, resulting in the formation of the corresponding merodicarbo- and merotricarbo-cyanines ($n = 2, 3$).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(4-Acetanilido-1:3-butadienyl)-4-phenylthiazole Methiodide.—4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.17 g., 1 M) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.58 g., 1M) in acetic anhydride (12 c.c.) were refluxed for 1½ hrs. The dark product was treated with an excess of ether and the gummy mass was solidified by keeping it in contact with methanol. The product was recrystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 53.94; H, 4.21. $C_{22}H_{21}ON_2IS$ requires C, 54.11; H, 4.30%).

5-[4-(3-Methyl-4-phenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-buten-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The preceding methiodide (4.88 g., 1 M) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g., 1 M) were refluxed in acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) in presence of fused sodium acetate for about 3 hrs. The product after being treated with cold water was washed with acetone to remove tarry products. The acetone-washed product was finally recrystallised twice from hot methanol, m.p. 225-27° (decomp.), yield 42%. (Found: C, 58.88; H, 4.52. $C_{19}H_{18}ON_2S_3$ requires C, 59.06; H, 4.66%).

2-(4-Acetanilido-1:3-butadienyl)-4-p-methoxyphenylthiazole Methiodide.—4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.47 g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.58 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 2 hours. Excess of acetic anhydride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the dark product was treated with ether. The gummy mass, thus obtained, after being washed with acetone, was solidified by keeping in contact with methanol. The product, thus obtained, was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by two more recrystallisations from acetic acid, m.p. 142-43° (decomp.), yield 50%. (Found: C, 53.06; H, 4.31. $C_{23}H_{23}O_2N_2IS$ requires C, 53.28; H, 4.44%).

5-[4-(3-Methyl-4-p-methoxyphenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-buten-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The above methiodide (5.18 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were heated under reflux in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for about 2½ hours. The product was washed with cold water, followed by acetone to remove tarry products. The product was purified by two recrystallisations from hot methanol, m.p. 163-65° (decomp.), yield 38%. (Found: C, 57.49; H, 4.68. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_2S_3$ requires C, 57.69; H, 4.80%).

2-(4-Acetanilido-1:3-butadienyl)-4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazole Methiodide.—A mixture of 4-p-ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.61 g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.58 g.) was heated similarly as above. The dark residue was treated with ether and the product was washed with acetone and crystallised from methanol, m.p. 142-13° (decomp.), yield 45%. (Found: C, 54.02; H, 4.57. $C_{21}H_{22}O_2N_2S$ requires C, 54.14; H, 4.70%).

5-[4-(3-Methyl-4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-buten-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The preceding methiodide (5.32 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for about one hour. The product after being washed with water was treated with a mixture of ether and methanol. The pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from hot methanol, m.p. 193-95° (decomp.), yield 38%. (Found: C, 58.48; H, 5.02. $C_{21}H_{22}O_2N_2S_2$ requires C, 58.60; H, 5.11%).

2-(4-Acetanilido-1:3-butadienyl)-4-p-bromophenylthiazole methiodide was prepared by heating under reflux a mixture of 4-p-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.96 g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.58 g.) in acetic anhydride for 1½ hrs. After removing the excess of the solvent under reduced pressure, the product was extracted with methanol. Removal of methanol resulted in the separation of the product which was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by two more recrystallisations from acetic acid, m.p. 75-78° (decomp.), yield 52%. (Found: C, 46.38; H, 3.39. $C_{22}H_{20}ON_2BrS$ requires C, 46.56; H, 3.52%).

5-[4-(3-Methyl-4-p-bromophenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-buten-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The preceding methiodide (5.67 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 70 minutes. The product after being washed with water was washed with acetone. The acetone-washed product was finally recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 151-52° (decomp.), yield 44%. (Found: C, 48.92; H, 3.54. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_2BrS_2$ requires C, 49.03; H, 3.65%).

2-(4-Acetanilido-1:3-butadienyl)-benzothiazole Methiodide.—2-Methylbenzothiazole methiodide (2.91 g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.58 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 1½ hrs. The dark product was treated repeatedly with ether and the gummy residue obtained was solidified by keeping it in contact with methanol. The product thus obtained was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from acetic acid, m.p. 160-62° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 51.82; H, 4.02. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_2S$ requires C, 51.95; H, 4.11%).

5-[4-(3-Methylbenzothiazolin-2-ylidene)-buten-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The above methiodide (4.62 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 2 hrs. The product after being washed with water was treated with acetone to remove tarry products and finally recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 173-74° (decomp.), yield 42%. (Found: C, 56.45; H, 4.32. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 56.66; H, 4.44%).

2-(6-Acetanilido-1:3-5-hexatrienyl)-4-phenylthiazole Methiodide.—4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.17 g.) and glutaconic aldehyde dianilide hydrochloride

(2.84 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 70 minutes. Excess of the solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the dark product treated with ether, followed by acetone. The acetone-washed product was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from acetic acid, m.p. 182° (decomp.), yield 52%. (Found: C, 55.96; H, 4.41; I, 24.62. $C_{24}H_{23}ON_2IS$ requires C, 56.03; H, 4.47; I, 24.70%).

5-[6-(3-Methyl-4-phenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-hexa-2:4-dien-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The same procedure was followed by refluxing the preceding methiodide (5.14 g., 1 M) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g., 1 M) in acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. The product was isolated in the manner described earlier and recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 145-46° (decomp.), yield 45%. (Found: C, 50.87; H, 3.75. $C_{20}H_{20}ON_2S_3$ requires C, 51.33; H, 3.87%).

2-(6-Acetanilido-1:3:5-hexatrienyl)-4-p-methoxyphenylthiazole Methiodide.—4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.47 g.) and glutamic aldehyde dianilide hydrochloride (2.84 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 70 minutes. The dark product was treated with excess of ether and the gummy mass so obtained was solidified by keeping it in contact with methanol. The product was recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 193-95° (decomp.), yield 50%. (Found: C, 55.01; H, 4.48. $C_{25}H_{25}O_2N_2IS$ requires C, 55.14; H, 4.59%).

5-[6-(3-Methyl-4-p-methoxyphenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-hexa-2:4-dien-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The preceding methiodide (5.44 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. The product after being washed with water was treated with acetone to remove tarry products. The acetone-washed product was finally recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 146-48° (decomp.), yield 44%. (Found: C, 59.62; H, 4.84. $C_{21}H_{22}O_2N_2S_3$ requires C, 59.73; H, 4.97%).

2-(6-Acetanilido-1:3:5-hexatrienyl)-4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazole Methiodide.—4-p-Ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.61 g.) and glutamic aldehyde dianilide hydrochloride (2.84 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 1 hr. The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the dark residue was treated with ether, followed by acetone. The acetone-washed product was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from acetic acid, m.p. 145-46° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 55.68; H, 4.73. $C_{26}H_{27}O_2N_2IS$ requires C, 55.93; H, 4.84%).

5-[6-(3-Methyl-4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-hexa-2:4-dien-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one was prepared in the same manner by refluxing the preceding methiodide (5.56 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) in acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. The product after being washed with water, followed by acetone, was recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 178-80° (decomp.), yield 46%. (Found: C, 60.39; H, 5.13. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2S_3$ requires C, 60.52; H, 5.26%).

2-(6-Acetanilido-1:3:5-hexatrienyl)-4-p-bromophenylthiazole methiodide was prepared from 4-p-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.96 g.) in the same way as the preceding ones. After removing the excess of acetic anhydride under reduced

pressure, the product was isolated in the manner described earlier and recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 87-88° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 48.24; H, 3.60. $C_{24}H_{22}ON_2BrIS$ requires C, 48.56; H, 3.71%).

5-[6-(3-Methyl-4-p-bromophenylthiazolin-2-ylidene)-hexa-2:4-dien-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The above methiodide (5.93 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 1 hr. The product was washed with water, followed by acetone to remove tarry products. The acetone-washed product was finally recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 222-23° (decomp.), yield 45%. (Found: C, 50.87; H, 3.75. $C_{20}H_{19}ON_2BrS_2$ requires C, 51.33; H, 3.87%).

2-(6-Acetanilido-1:3:5-hexatrienyl)-benzothiazole Methiodide.—2-Methylbenzothiazole methiodide (2.91 g.) and glutamic aldehyde dianilide hydrochloride (2.84 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 70 minutes. The dark product was treated with ether and the gummy mass so obtained was solidified by keeping it in contact with methanol. The product, thus obtained, was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by recrystallisation from acetic acid, m.p. 163° (decomp.), yield 52%. (Found: C, 54.02; H, 4.22. $C_{22}H_{21}ON_2IS$ requires C, 54.11; H, 4.30%).

5-[6-(3-Methylbenzothiazolin-2-ylidene)-hexa-2:4-dien-1-ylidene]-3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one.—The above methiodide (4.88 g.) and 3-ethyl-2-thiothiazolid-4-one (1.61 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate for 70 minutes. The product after being thoroughly washed with water, followed by acetone to remove tarry products, was finally recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 208-10° (decomp.), yield 44%. (Found: C, 58.88; H, 4.53. $C_{19}H_{18}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 59.06; H, 4.66%).

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